

THE EFFICACY OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION IN CHILD UPBRINGING

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the role of education in forming the spiritual and moral worldview of children in preschool educational organizations. Emphasizes that the teacher's scientific potential and pedagogical skills are key factors for children's spiritual development. The article discusses various approaches to the concept of spirituality, the continuity between the family and preschools, and the importance of organizing the educational process through interactive methods and play-based activities.

The role of education is immensely significant in influencing the human spiritual spirit and strengthening its foundations. The quality of the education provided is directly dependent on the knowledge, erudition, talent, and methodological diversity of the educators in preschool educational organizations.

For this reason, in order to continuously expand the scope and range of their knowledge, educators must consistently and systematically familiarize themselves with scientific innovations. They should independently demonstrate the potential of the educational process in preschool organizations regarding spiritual-moral upbringing, clearly define the goals and objectives of activity centers in this regard, and possess the skills to design the educational process to achieve guaranteed results.

The activity of spiritual-moral upbringing of the child initiated in the family is continued within the preschool educational organization (PEO) through two interconnected and mutually reinforcing processes—education and upbringing—in a purposeful and scientifically grounded manner. The educational process possesses significant potential for forming the elements of spiritual-moral upbringing in children. However, there are specific and unique opportunities for activity in the spiritual-moral upbringing of children.

A person's spirituality consists of their manners, conduct, ethics, and culture. The more an individual possesses refined behavior and good virtues, the more spiritually mature they are considered to be. Manners, as a form of human perfection, awaken love in youth toward their elders and lead to the elimination of disrespect, arrogance, discrimination, rudeness, and other traits that cause various miseries and suffering.

The word "spirituality" (ma'naviyat) is a comprehensive concept that has been attracting the attention of many sociologists, literary critics, ethicists, art historians, and

scientists from other fields. Consequently, the definitions given to this concept are diverse. Below are some examples of these:

Spirituality is the internal and external world of a human being;

Spirituality is the hallmark of a nation;

Spirituality is the light within the human heart;

Spirituality is the totality of a person's psychological and intellectual world;

Spirituality is a concept that embodies the inner life, psychological experiences, mental abilities, and perception of a society, nation, or individual;

Specific qualities in the human spiritual world that can acquire positive social significance are called spirituality.

In the land of Transoxiana (Movarounnahr), which was home to Abu Rayhon Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sino, and many other scholars whose names and works have been forgotten, many scientists who added masterpieces to the treasury of natural sciences have emerged even in our time. Among them are many worthy representatives who have spread the fame of the Uzbek people to the world.

The role of education in influencing the human spiritual spirit and strengthening it is boundlessly great. The extent to which education is delivered depends directly on the knowledge, erudition, talent, and methodological diversity of preschool educators. Therefore, to instill elements of spirituality, preschool educators must constantly broaden their scope of knowledge and regularly keep pace with scientific advancements.

The effectiveness of spiritual-moral knowledge also largely depends on the content, means, and methods of education. The methods of presenting spiritual knowledge should be selected based on the socio-psychological capacities of children of each age group. Introducing children to spiritual knowledge should be of an introductory nature. It is appropriate to emphasize specific elementary spiritual upbringing for children of this age. Spiritual-moral upbringing should be presented in an imaginative, emotional, and interesting game format using interactive methods. In presenting spiritual-moral knowledge, not only what is given to the children but also how it is given is of great importance.

In order to more deeply instill spiritual knowledge into the child's mind, it is advisable to provide them with various games, competitions, dramatizations, and educational tasks.

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